

SPACE AND TERRESTRIAL TRANSMISSION SYSTEMS IN TACTICAL C3 ARCHITECTURES

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Tactical command and control relies heavily on communications and hence, transmission systems. To understand this relationship one must know the tactical command and control function, the peculiarities of tactical communications, and the characteristics of present day tactical space and terrestrial transmission systems. Key elements of these subject areas are discussed and the current transmission architecture, supporting tactical command and control, is outlined.

Tactical C3 Architecture

An architecture is a basic design which combines practical, technological, and esthetical principles into a harmonious whole. So, what has tactical C3 to do with architecture? Architectures, in the context of tactical C3 can have three functions. First, an architecture can show how the organizational elements of the Services gather, process, and disseminate information in the exercise of tactical command and control. Such an architecture identifies who needs to exchange information with whom, and what information needs to be exchanged in order to accomplish a tactical mission. It is a design for a distributed process (accomplishment of a tactical mission) that requires interconnectivity (communications) between the various processing stations (command and control elements). Second, an architecture can show how the various C2 and communications systems serving the command and control elements, have to work together in a practical sense, exploiting technology to the fullest, in order to accomplish a tactical mission. Such an architecture is a design for a "system of systems", so to speak. Third, an architecture can be a design for an acquisition process. Here it shows which C3 systems must be selected for acquisitions and at what time and in what sequence they must be fielded, to ensure the most effective and efficient accomplishment of a tactical mission, within a given budget. Such an architecture develops an investment strategy. In the following we will consider only the second type of architecture: The system of systems.

Tactical Command Control and Communications

What do we mean by tactical C3? Command and control is exercised by people over people. Systems are used to exercise command and control: command and control systems, and communication systems. The distinction between C2 and communications systems is necessary if interoperability between unlike systems is a requirement - as it frequently is. Command and control systems are used by people to collect, process, and generate information, and disseminate it to others so that they may exercise their required command and control. Communications systems provide the means to transport information between people and their C2 systems. In some specialized systems communications is an inherent part of the command and control system. Hence the term C3 system. Yet, today in the exercise of tactical command and control these specialized cases are rare. Therefore, we will use the term C3 system to include the combination of people, their organizations, their C2 systems (which, today, are mostly a combination of paper, pencil, and telephone), and their communication systems.

Command: The function of command is well understood. The commander, a person put in charge and given full authority over a segment of forces, issues directives regarding what needs to be done, when it needs to be done, and who will do it. In order to do this he needs to know the status of his and the enemy's forces, and be able to estimate the difficulties and risks involved in carrying out his commands. All of this needs communications, and the timely and accurate compilation and presentation of all information that can have an impact on the commanders decision. This function is very much like that performed by a manager within a corporation. The enemy's role is transformed to that of the manager's competition.

Control: The function of Control is not as readily understood. Control is what it takes to make subordinates do what was directed, and it involves, primarily, leadership. In the military, control includes the emotional motivation of the soldiers to fully support their commanders.

to fight and, to risk their lives for a common and worth while cause. Control in corporate management is more rational and uses primarily material benefits as motivating factors, while emotional factors are secondary.

Thus, the tactical commander must demonstrate and communicate leadership in the most idealistic sense, to his subordinates. Because of the wide dispersion between commanders and subordinates in the tactical environment, elaborate communications are needed to accomplish control.

Communications: Communications, the third C of C3 is well understood, but difficult to establish and to maintain on the tactical battlefield. Command and control depend on good communications, and good communications, in turn, depends on reliable, highly mobile, easy to set up, and easy to operate terminal and transmission equipment.

Tactical Transmission

The tactical environment places special demands on transmission technology. It cannot tolerate the wide band, complex to set up, permanently installed transmission links of the commercial sector. Even though the commercial and tactical transmission technologies used appear similar in both, there are significant differences which impact on frequencies used, channel and link capacities, and the overall design of tactical communications systems.

Terrestrial Transmission

The Army has metallic cable transmission systems and is developing a replacement system that uses optical fiber. These systems are intended for use in relatively stable situations where major command elements stay in place for relatively long periods of time. In general, they are not suitable for the volatile and changing tactical environment. The tactical Army relies on radio transmission systems to satisfy its communication requirements. These systems are based on radio frequency propagation, and are categorized as single and multi channel transmission systems.

Single Channel Systems

Single channel transmission systems carry but one channel of communications. This channel can be used in a point to point configuration or, more often, is shared by a number of users in a so called net configuration. In a net configuration, at any one time, only one participant can talk (transmit), and all the others must listen (receive).

Single Channel Nets: Nets are ideal configurations for command communications (command nets). The commander issues an order to a particular subordinate, while all other subordinates listen in for instant coordination. Matters of execution can be explained and questions resolved while simultaneously being coordinated. Command nets are in wide spread use on the battlefield. Logistics and administrative functions also use single channel nets but, because of limitations in available frequencies, and the fact that these functions can usually tolerate short delays, several functions often share one channel. Such a net is similar to a party line. While one function makes use of the net, the others have to wait their turn for access to the net. Command and control, because of its higher priority, and almost zero tolerance for delays, usually has a dedicated net, not shared with any other tactical function, for each echelon of command, or commander.

Single Channel Characteristics: Because of the geographical dispersion of net participants, single channel systems must often transmit omnidirectionally. Additionally, transmission to all net participants must be possible whether there is unimpeded line of sight, trees, buildings, or masking terrain between the transmitter and receiver. Because of this requirement, the radio frequencies selected

for tactical command and control, communications are generally in the VHF band below 100MHz. Frequencies at the lower end of this band perform best in the unpredictable tactical environment. The total number of channels (nets) that can be squeezed into this band, however, is relatively small. The total number available depends on the channel bandwidth that is used in the radio system. The narrower the bandwidth, the more channels there will be, for us, our allies, our enemies, and a host of civil functions. Thanks to the propagation characteristics of VHF frequencies on the ground (signal strength diminishes with the fourth power of the distance), the range of VHF transmissions with reasonable power levels (about 16 watts), and omnidirectional antennas, is limited to about 30 miles. This helps to relieve the frequency crunch by allowing the same frequency to be used about every 100 miles. But using the same VHF radio in an aircraft, at an altitude where free space propagation applies (signal strength diminishes with the square of the distance), and the ground propagation inhibitors are absent, will make a shambles of any frequency management plan. Therefore, single channel radios on aircraft most often make use of the high VHF band (above 100 MHz) and the lower UHF band (300 to 400 MHz), and restrict transmission to relatively low powered radios.

Multi Channel Systems

Multi channel radio systems carry large numbers of channels between communications nodes, where these channels are switched to the destinations desired. The large channel groups, and the ability of a particular subscriber to make use of any channel in a group, give multi channel systems an efficient traffic handling capability. On the other hand, the high traffic handling efficiency of multi channel systems make them more sensitive to the loss of any one link. Therefore, tactical multi channel systems robustness is important, and these systems are routinely over designed so that in case of link loss, which can be a frequent occurrence, the remaining and redundant portions of the network can handle the traffic load.

In comparison, in the commercial world, the capacity of each link is maximized, but the network is not over designed. In maximizing channel numbers per link, radios are designed to operate at ever higher frequencies. Digital technology makes maximizing channel numbers possible, even though it causes a sixteen fold increase (64 Kbps pulse code modulation (PCM) in digital technology, versus 4KHz in analog technology) in individual channel bandwidth. But at the highest radio frequency ranges, bandwidth hardly matters. The fast growth of optical fiber transmission systems, with their huge bandwidth, as supplement to the high capacity digital radios, encourages further bandwidth squandering.

Tactical Frequencies: In the tactical area bandwidth does matter. Cable and optical fiber transmission systems are cumbersome and generally unsuitable in a highly mobile environment. Tactical multi channel systems rely on line of sight (LOS) radio for transmission. The higher frequencies used in commercial systems require a perfectly clear path, a solid antenna mount, and a very precise antenna adjustment; characteristics which are next to impossible to achieve in a tactical situation. Therefore, tactical LOS systems use frequencies in the UHF band below 2GHz, and, in the division operation area, below 400 MHz. These frequency selections allow for the penetration of some foliage, and allow antennas to be hidden in treelines. The relatively wide beam width of the radiated signal can tolerate imprecise antenna adjustments, and swaying antenna supports (masts). Thus, these lower frequencies tend to compensate for the unavoidable inaccuracy of installation that is inherent to the constant movement, and extremely short installation times allowed on the tactical battlefield.

Tactical Channel Capacity: The analog technology, that was introduced into military multi channel communications during the 1950s proved difficult to maintain in the tactical environment. This fact, together with the need to secure and encrypt military transmissions, made the use of digital technology in tactical systems a necessity. The introduction of digital technology into the tactical multi channel systems increased the nominal channel bandwidth ratio by a factor of twelve (48 Kbps PCM versus 4 KHz analog), but the actual transmission bandwidth increased by less than a factor of two, due to the lower signal to noise ratio (S/N) tolerated by digital transmission systems and the bandwidth efficient digital modulation scheme used. The switch from 48 Kbps PCM channels, as used in the Army Tactical

Communications System (ATACS), to the 16 Kbps Continuously Variable Slope Delta modulation (CVSD) used in TRI-TAC and the Mobile Subscriber Equipment (MSE) of the Army, brought an effective doubling of the channel capacity over that of the tactical multi channel systems of the fifties. Yet, given the bandwidth and frequency availability of tactical terrestrial transmission systems, channel capacity remains scarce in the tactical environment.

Terrestrial Transmission Systems

Terrestrial transmission systems have the advantage of being completely under the control of the tactical commander. Single channel systems are organic to the troops and are ideal for command net communications among people. But the demand for frequencies, the difficulty of assigning and managing the available frequencies, and the unintentional and intentional interference among them present serious restrictions. Terrestrial multi channel systems are installed and operated by signal troops, under the control of and responsive to the tactical commander. Clever site and frequency selection will provide some degree of protection against enemy counter measures, and can be used to add robustness to the multi channel network. Site selection is complicated by the actual deployment of friendly troops and their planned movements. Signal sites and troop locations often do not correspond. For best LOS propagation, transmission sites must be somewhat exposed, and on a hill or a slope, while troops are likely to stay deep in the valley, or in built up areas. Therefore, in multi channel systems, some interconnect links between the signal sites and troop concentrations are needed. The same frequency characteristics discussed above are desirable but, because of the severe limitation in the availability of suitable frequencies, such interconnect links are generally provided by relatively short, millimeter wave links using optical siting techniques. Such links are now being tried in place of the previously used cable links.

Space Transmission

In space transmissions, a distinction is also made between single channel and multi channel systems. But, the global character and the emerging, more sophisticated sharing techniques necessary to make efficient use of the limited satellite repeater resources (bandwidth and power), do not permit the independent use of space transmission by any one commander. Instead, space segment resources are controlled at the highest possible levels, on a theater or national basis. This, at least potentially, restricts satellite systems availability in times of need, and causes operational commanders to plan for alternate communications means, should the resource be consumed by higher priority users.

Single Channel Space Based Systems

As with terrestrial systems, space systems can be used for net and point to point operations. A third operating mode is the demand access mode. In this mode, a group of point to point links and nets share a pool of frequencies or time division multiple access (TDMA) time slots. Assuming that at any one time only a certain percentage of links and nets is in use (busy), there is no need to provide more frequencies than are in use at any one time. This mode makes more efficient use of the available resources (frequencies), but at the cost of requiring more complex protocols to gain access to a channel (frequency or time slot), and the delays required to execute the protocols. Single channel extraction, though possible, does become more complex at higher carrier frequencies. Therefore, our present tactical single channel space transmission systems operate in the UHF band. These lower frequencies demand larger antennas to achieve usable signal strengths. While smaller configurations are available, single channel satellite transmission systems are best suited for use on more substantial platforms, such as ships and aircraft.

Multi Channel Space Based Systems

Multi channel satellite transmission systems for tactical use have added new dimensions to tactical communications. Demand access is also possible with multi channel systems, allowing any user who demands access for a call to get a channel as long as there is one idle at the users access location (ground terminal serving the user). Demand access systems can be viewed as a space based switching node with access trunks terminated at each ground terminal. Different designs

have been proposed and the actual switching function can be performed on the ground or in space. No demand access systems has, so far, been successfully fielded.

Another idea which has significant tactical applications, is the hub - spoke concept of interconnections. Here, the command structure of the ground forces is duplicated by the transmission system. Picture a corps deployment with the corps command post at the hub of operations and the divisions forming the spokes (even if they are all on one side of the hub). Tactical satellite transmission systems favor such an arrangement and the Ground Mobile Forces Satellite Communications (GMFSC) system does implement it. Point to point tactical satellite multi channel links are rarely used.

Space Transmission Systems

The use of satellite transmission systems on the tactical battlefield entails unique problems. Space antenna 'foot prints' become a very important consideration. The antenna footprint is that area on the ground which would be "illuminated" by the satellite antenna, were the radio frequencies, emitted by the satellite, beams of light. Any transmitter and receiver within that footprint has excellent access to a satellite's transmissions, or for sending a signal to the satellite. This is also true for an enemy who wants either to listen or to jam satellite signals. If the enemy is within the footprint, it is relatively easy for him to jam, disturb, overload, or spoof our transmissions. Therefore, it is very important to adjust the footprint so that the enemy is outside the print. Such footprint adjustments make the use of satellite terminals near the forward edge of the battle area difficult. This problem is significantly reduced by multi beam and null steering satellite antennas. Another problem is the limited frequency band and power capacity presently available for tactical use. To deal with this limitation, strict planning for, and control of these resources is a necessity.

Summary and Conclusions

What can we conclude from all this? Obviously, we have confirmed that effective tactical command and control depends on good communications and in turn, on reliable transmission systems. Today we use terrestrial as well as satellite transmission systems, in both single and multi channel modes, to provide the robust communications support needed by tactical command and control. Over the years a tactical transmission architecture has emerged which makes the most of each transmission media's specific characteristics.

- Single channel, terrestrial VHF nets for direct command and control of land combat.
- Single channel, terrestrial UHF nets for direct command and control of combat in the air.
- Single channel, satellite UHF nets for command and control of the battle at sea, or to execute the initial phases of single service and joint force contingency actions.
- Multi channel, terrestrial networks for command and control of forces on land, and to serve combat support and combat service support activities.
- Multi channel, satellite systems to support the higher echelon command and control structure, especially in widely dispersed situations.

This outlined transmission architecture, which supports tactical command and control, is primarily based on the physical characteristics of the propagation media and, to a lesser degree, on the technology used in implementation. As technology evolves, we can expect to see significant changes in this architecture.